

Research

Recovery of Cellulose Fibers from Waste Books and Writing Paper by Flotation De-inking

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Abstract: Waste books and writing paper are low-cost and convenient sources of fibre for manufacturing paper. The current study aims to characterize the chemical and enzymatic deinking of waste books and writing papers. It describes the research leading to the development of a process for floatation deinking of waste paper. All the experiments were run under the same conditions and equipment. The chemical deinking of waste paper demonstrated a high deinking efficiency on writing paper, but a low deinking efficiency was obtained with waste books. Enzymatic treatments significantly improved the drainage rate of the deinked waste papers. Both chemical and enzymatic deinking increased the brightness of waste books and writing paper. The efficiency of the process is evaluated in terms of yield of clean pulp, brightness, tensile index, tear strength, burst strength, folding, thickness, etc. Chemical and Enzymatic treatment caused a 10% reduction in the tear index for waste books but a 9% improvement in writing papers. The tensile index was increased by 5.7% and 3.8% in writing papers and waste books relative to the non-treated sample. In addition, enzymatic treatment increased the 19.45% tensile index relative to non-treated waste books. However, the writing paper showed the highest reduction in the tensile index relative to the blank. Taken together, these results showed an improvement in the optical and physical properties of all paper sheets produced in this study.

Keywords: Chemical deinking, Enzymatic deinking, Flotation process, Pulping, Recycling, Waste paper

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Introduction

Pulp is the processed basic raw material for paper, board, and other packaging substances (Bajpai, 2015). The pulp and paper industry is one of the largest industries in the world (Rullifank et al., 2020). The North American, Northern European and East Asian countries predominantly govern it. Latin America and Australia also have significant pulp and paper industries and from Asia, both India and China are expected to become new key players in the industry's

growth (Chauhan & Meena, 2021; Haile et al., 2023; Kong et al., 2016; Ojala et al., 2013). The global production of paper and paperboard is estimated to be around 406 million tons and is expected to soar even higher in recent years (Haile et al., 2023). Worldwide, over 300 million tons of paper are used annually, indicating a 400% increase in paper consumption growth over the previous 40 years (Ezeudu et al., 2019). The growth rate of paper consumption is comparatively faster in Asia; it accounts for almost 40% of total world paper and paperboard production, whereas the European Union (EU) and North America account for about one quarter each (Furszyfer Del Rio et al., 2022; Karikallio et al., 2011).

Environmental concerns have permeated practically every facet of the manufacturing sector and every stage of a product's life cycle during the past years. As environmental issues gain more attention, producers must enhance the value of their goods while lessening their negative effects on the environment (Appannagari, 2017). Researchers suggest that remanufacturing goods and utilizing recyclable materials are two ways to reduce environmental impact since remanufacturing increases value and preserves the shape of returnable products, recycling allows materials and their components to be reused. (Cheung & Pachisia, 2015). The majority of global recycling and remanufacturing research efforts are concentrated on the automotive, aerospace, and electronics sectors while much less focus has been paid to the paper industry despite it demonstrating a consistent upward trend over the past few years (Čabalová et al., 2021; Han et al., 2021; Liu et al., 2020; Rene et al., 2021; Thamizh Selvan et al., 2021).

Paper recycling is a method that creates new paper products from packaging trash or used paper. As long as there has been paper, recycling has existed. The advantages of recycling for the environment and the economy have long been understood by paper firms (Cabalova et al., 2011; Laurijssen et al., 2010; Villanueva & Wenzel, 2007). One of the biggest global pollutants of water is the paper industry. Recycling paper can not only eradicate hazardous contaminants, it can also diminish air pollution by 74% and reduce water pollution by 35% (Bahrami & Jafari, 2020; Mismán et al., 2008). In recent years, paper recycling has become popular with everyone to help the environment by reusing our resources and conserving landfill space. One ton of recycled paper saves 3.3 cubic yards of landfill, 7000 gallons of water, 380 gallons of oil, 4000 kilowatts of energy and 17 trees (V. Kumar, 2017; Pivnenko et al., 2015). Both the forestry industry and the environment greatly benefit from pulp recycling. Depending on the quality of the paper or packaging materials produced, pulp may be recycled up to 7 or 10 times by adding a specific percentage of new pulp. (Bajpai, 2010).

Bangladesh is a densely populated country. The pulp and paper industry is one of the highest energy-consuming industries in the country and currently, the nation produces 1.5 million metric tons of paper annually (Shakil & Mostafa, 2023). There are 128 pulp and paper mills in Bangladesh and they produce paper products from recycled paper and imported pulp (Siddique et al., 2022). The only state-owned pulp-producing mill in Bangladesh is Karnaphuli Paper Mills (KPM) which produces only 12,000 metric tons of pulp and 30,000 metric tons of paper product per year (Quader, 2012; M. M. Rahman & Kabir, 2010). But recently, a lack of sufficient supplies of fibrous raw materials, a scarcity of raw materials, and technical difficulties have also made KPM reliant on imported pulp and recycled paper (Kamali & Khodaparast, 2015; S. Rahman & Uddin, 2022; Sarkar et al., 2021). As of right now, Bangladesh does not have any additional pulp production facilities and with the steady development of the country, pulp's numerous applications and needs have grown gradually. From 2015 to 2020, the imported amount of pulp has increased from 200,000 metric tons to 500,000 metric tons (Sikder et al., 2022). Therefore, even though Bangladesh's pulp and paper industries are producing high-quality papers, they're now concentrating on streamlining their recycling procedure from an environmental, economic, and process development standpoint.

Due to the preservation of forests and rising environmental awareness, research interest in new renewable sources for the pulp and pulping industries has increased recently. Bangladesh is a tropical Southeast Asian country with marginal forestland which barely covers 10-11% of the country, it shoulders a significant shortage of forest resources (Ali Reza & Kamrul Hasan, 2020). The majority of the demand is therefore satisfied by recycling used paper products. (Anuj Kumar et al., 2021). Because virgin pulp has longer fibres than recycled pulp, it produces paper products of a higher grade.

However, recycled pulp can also be used to produce quality paper products by blending it with a specific percentage of virgin pulp. Although cellulose fibres are used as the primary raw material in the production of paper, waste papers can also be used as an alternative source of such (Karthikeyan & Krishnamoorthy, 2021). The main problem, however, with recyclable paper production is the removal of ink particles and ink residues from the waste papers (de-inking) and hence, it is mandatory to get rid of any ink particles and non-ink contaminants from waste papers (Fatemeh, 2022; Amit Kumar & Dutt, 2021).

In this study, the goal was to examine the current waste paper recycling procedure and, consequently, to investigate a recycling process that would include an economical and efficient de-inking method—the most crucial stage in waste paper recycling. This method will use less chemicals to retain the original pulp quality using peroxide (H_2O_2) in combination with sodium hydroxide ($NaCl$), foaming agent and enzyme. Therefore, our suggested procedure will also be effective and economical in addition to being environmentally friendly.

Methods and Methodology

Sample Collection

Waste paper samples were collected from the curbsides and/or vendors from different areas of Chattogram including Mansurabad, University of Chittagong, Muradpur, Halishahar and Chaktai.

Experimental Site

This experiment was conducted in the Pulp and Paper Division Laboratory of Bangladesh Forest Research Institute. It is located at 22.3742 °N 91.8270 °E of Chattogram city.

Chemicals and Reagents

In this research, Surf Excel (1%) (Local brand of a commercial detergent powder) was used as a surfactant. Sodium hydroxide ($NaOH$), Ammonium hydroxide (NH_4OH) (2%) and Xylanase enzyme (0.02g) were used in combination with hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) during the pulping stage of waste books and writing paper.

Methodology

Pulping of the waste paper was performed in a disintegrator (Hydro pulper) for 15 minutes at 3% consistency. All the chemical reagents were used in proportion to the dry paperweight. The temperature was maintained at 40-55°C (Luo et al., 2003). After pulping, the screened pulp is transferred to a cell tank for floatation deinking. The pulp stream of waste book and writing paper is mixed with hydrogen peroxide, sodium hydroxide, surfactant, and enzyme respectively at varying consistency (Moon & Nagarajan, 1998). The pH is maintained at 9.0-10.0 and the temperature is set at 50°C. Until it is ready for the final processing step, the pulp is bleached several times at this point. Next, hand sheets were made from the cleaned and beaten pulp in a standard Tappi hand sheet mould and pressed using a standard Tappi press method. The physical properties such as Tensile Index, Tear Index, Burst index, Folding Endurance and Brightness were measured after conditioning at 50% relative humidity and 23°C (El-khalek, 2012).

Results and Discussion

Kappa number evaluation

The kappa number in the floatation of waste books dropped as chemical concentration increased. Waste books pulp had a blank kappa number of 25.23, however, when H_2O_2 was used at 1, 2 and 3%, it steadily fell to 22.78, 22.07 and 21.86 (Table 1). The kappa number of enzymatic treatments was 23.55. As opposed to chemical treatment, it was quite good. In Table 1, the kappa number of writing papers declined from 5.02 to 4.12 as peroxide doses increased from 1 to 3%. The Xylanase enzyme was used and obtained the kappa number 4.84.

Table 1: Kappa numbers of Waste Books and Writing Paper

Waste Books (WB)		Writing Paper (WP)	
Treatment	Kappa number	Treatment	Kappa number
Blank	25.23	Blank	6.14
Detergent	24.38	Detergent	5.09
1% H ₂ O ₂	22.78	1% H ₂ O ₂	5.02
2% H ₂ O ₂	22.07	2% H ₂ O ₂	4.78
3% H ₂ O ₂	21.86	3% H ₂ O ₂	4.12
Enzyme	23.54	Enzyme	4.84

Tensile Index

Writing paper had some of the highest tensile strength in 2% concentration of H₂O₂ (32.87 Nm/g) and detergent treatment (32.28 Nm/g) shown in **Table 2**, yet Waste Books obtained high tensile strength in enzymatic treatment (34.50 Nm/g) (**Table 2**). (Machmud et al., 2013) found an ultimate tensile strength of 232.5 (kgf/cm²) in office copy paper (A4) whereas (Green, 2012) found a 26.7 Nm/g tensile index in laser-printed office waste papers. The tensile index value of the present study was 45-60 mN/g for the newsprint paper. Differences between waste books and writing paper tensile index were illustrated in **Figure 1&2**. A group of scientists has shown the effect of cellulose and hemicellulose on the cellulosic fiber of recycling paper, which showed higher tensile strength with a reduced tear index (Saxena & Singh Chauhan, 2017). Deinked pulp's strength properties were affected to some extent when cellulose and hemicellulose, alone or in combination, were applied in mill practice (Bajpai, 1999). When the concentration of H₂O₂ was increased cellulose degradation was also increased so tensile strength decreased drastically at higher dose peroxide.

Figure-1: Tensile Index (Nm/g) of Writing Paper (WP)

Figure-2: Tensile Index (Nm/g) of Waste Books (WB)

Table 2: Tensile Index of writing papers and waste books

Treatment	Tensile Index (Nm/g) of Writing Paper (WP)		Tensile Index (Nm/g) of Waste Books (WB)	
	CSF(mL)		CSF(mL)	
	250	450	250	450
Detergent	52.46	25.28	44.92	26.20
1% H ₂ O ₂	45.65	2.17	20.77	20.47
2% H ₂ O ₂	45.51	27.17	53.37	41.15
3% H ₂ O ₂	60.31	21.67	43.44	33.28
Enzyme (0.02g)	23.43	46.13	25.76	20.08
Control	40.57	7.07	39.90	9.14

Tear Index

The tearing test, also known as the Elmendorf tear test, gauges a paper's internal resistance to tearing instead of its ability to withstand edge-tear stresses. The force vertical to the paper's level required to rip a single sheet through a predetermined distance after the tear has already begun is known as internal tearing resistance. A tear's initiating force is determined by the edge-tearing strength. The force needed to start a tear may be multiple times greater than the force required to continue it once it has begun. High edge-tearing strength is also exhibited by papers and other materials that show high tensile stretch or elongation to break. The high stretch makes it problematic to localize stress in an adequately small area so that a tear can be initiated.

The strength of the tears varied depending on fibre length. In the blank sample, the tear index for writing paper was 6.78 mNm²/g (Table 3) and for waste books, it was 7.07 mNm²/g (Table 3). However, using 2% concentrations of H₂O₂, both samples resulted from a higher tear index. In 3% concentration of H₂O₂, writing paper gave the highest reduction of tear strength. According to (Sheikhi et al., 2013), the tear index of recycled abbreviated pulp was 5.14 mNm²/g and the tear index of virgin bagasse pulp was 5.47 mNm²/g. In Figure 3 & 4, the tear strength of waste books was 7.45 mNm²/g and writing paper was 7.72 mNm²/g. Due to beating, the fibre quality of waste books was increased. Enzymatic treatment was environmentally friendly and broke fibre length slowly. So it gave a higher tear index in waste

books and writing paper. On the other hand, (Lee et al., 2007) found a 7.1 mNm²/g tear strength of enzymatic deinking of laser-printed office paper and (Green, 2012) found a 7.6 mNm²/g tensile index in waste paper.

Figure-3: Tear Index (mNm²/g) of Writing Paper (WP)

Figure-4: Tear Index (mNm²/g) of Waste Books (WB)

Table 3: Tear Index of writing papers and waste books

Treatment	Tear Index (mNm ² /g) of Writing Paper (WP)		Tear Index (mNm ² /g) of Waste Books (WB)	
	CSF(mL)		CSF(mL)	
	250	450	250	450
Detergent	6.51	6.16	7.06	7.18
1% H ₂ O ₂	7.64	5.80	7.79	5.95
2% H ₂ O ₂	7.32	7.20	6.53	7.19
3% H ₂ O ₂	7.29	7.13	6.34	6.52
Enzyme (0.02g)	6.33	4.13	6.67	6.01
Control	7.22	6.92	7.16	6.62

Folding Endurance

Folding endurance is a log of double fold at base 10 (Folding Endurance = Log_{10} (Double Folds)). Paper deterioration over time can be measured with folding endurance. When printing grades on paper that will be folded multiple times, such as in books, maps, or pamphlets, it is crucial. For cartons, box boards, ammonia print paper, cover paper, etc., the fold test is also crucial. For Bond, Ledger, Currency, Map, Blueprint, and Record Papers, high folding endurance is a must. Currency paper has the highest folding endurance (>10,000). Long and flexible fibers provide high folding endurance.

Folding endurance was increased by adding more chemicals in waste books. In the untreated sample, writing paper had a folding endurance of 14.6 and waste books had a folding endurance of 19.6 (Table 4, Figure 5 & 6). The highest folding endurance in waste books was 21.6 obtained from 2% H₂O₂ and in writing paper it was 23.6 which was obtained from 2% H₂O₂. Xylanase enzyme obtained 20.6 folding endurance and blank sheet of waste books obtained 11.4 folding endurance. Other treated folding endurance of waste books were 8.8, 20, 21.4 and 10.8 in detergent, 1, 2 and 3% H₂O₂ treatment respectively (Table 4).

Figure-5: Folding endurance (Log₁₀d) of Writing Paper (WP)

Figure-6: Folding endurance (Log₁₀d) of Waste Books (WB)

Table 4: Folding endurance of writing paper and waste books

Treatment	Folding endurance (Log ₁₀ d) of Writing Paper (WP)		Folding endurance (Log ₁₀ d) of Waste Books (WB)	
	CSF (mL)		CSF(mL)	
	250	450	250	450
Detergent	69.62	7.80	25.14	6.02
1% H ₂ O ₂	115.85	61.90	23.36	20.22
2% H ₂ O ₂	51.17	30.97	44.10	26.32
3% H ₂ O ₂	74.75	19.92	20.63	12.57
Enzyme (0.02g)	12.15	2.40	3.88	86.79
Control	45.00	73.57	27.91	33.27

Burst Index

Bursting strength measures the amount, percentage, and distribution of fibres in the paper; these factors are typically influenced by the method of preparation, length, quality, and addition of surface additives, as well as by beating and refining times. (ASTM 1963). By standardizing the bursting strength to the grammage, the burst index is obtained. (Rinaldo, 2020). The burst strength is an observational measurement and has no perfect definition. Nonetheless, there exists a slight mathematical and physical correlation between the burst strength and tensile strength and elongation (Rinaldo, 2020) and is frequently used in paper production to demonstrate the paper strength. Bursting strength, which is relatively easy to calculate, shows how long a piece of paper can withstand pressure.

In between waste books and writing paper, the burst index of writing paper was higher than that of waste books. The Burst index of waste books at 2% H₂O₂ concentration was 2.42 kPam²/g and for writing paper burst index was 2.64 kPam²/g at 2% H₂O₂ doses (**Table 5**). (Sheikhi et al., 2013) showed that the burst index of recycled OCE pulp is 0.633 kPam²/g and the burst index of virgin bagasse pulp was 2.63 kPam²/g. The burst and tensile strength depend on the inter-fibre bonding (Wistara & Hidayah, 2010). (Horn, 1978) indicate that more flexible fibres provide more areas that can be developed for bonding the fibre length.

Writing paper had a burst value of 2.13 kPa.m²/g and waste books had a burst index of 1.74 kPa.m²/g in the blank sample. Waste book burst index increased (1.94 kPa.m²/g in 1% concentration of H₂O₂), although writing paper burst index dropped (1.74 kPa.m²/g) (**Table 5**). The burst index increased 2.42 kPa.m²/g in waste books and 2.64 kPa.m²/g in writing paper when 2% concentrations of H₂O₂ are used in the sample testing. Writing paper had the highest reduction in burst strength (1.36 kPa.m²/g) at 3% H₂O₂ concentration. (Chutani & Sharma, 2015) found 1.52 kPa.m²/g burst index in ozone treated newspaper whereas the burst strength value of xylanase treated pulp was 1.35 kPa.m²/g. The changes in writing paper and waste books tear strength were shown in **Figure 7&8**.

Figure-7: Burst index of Writing Paper (WP)

Figure-8: Burst Index of Waste Books (WB)

Table 5: Burst index of writing paper and waste books

Treatment	Burst index of Writing Paper (WP)		Burst Index of Waste Books (WB)	
	CSF(mL)		CSF(mL)	
	250	450	250	450
Detergent	39.6	20.64	26.2	17.76
1% H ₂ O ₂	39.61	3.05	28.88	13.42
2% H ₂ O ₂	39.05	29.85	33.93	27.29
3% H ₂ O ₂	36.51	21.49	29.52	21.78
Enzyme (0.02g)	11.31	15.52	26.69	29.43
Control	28.72	3.56	27.87	1.87

Brightness

A paper’s brightness is scientifically measured in terms of how much blue light is reflected from it. Paper brightness is measured on a scale of 0 to 100. This scale determines how much light is reflected from the surface of a sheet of paper. The higher the number, the brighter the paper.

Blank waste books and writing paper had brightness values of 54.28 and 69.03 ISO respectively (**Table 6**). By increasing the chemical doses, it grew gradually. By raising the concentration of H₂O₂ (1 to 3%), the brightness of the waste books was raised from 56.13 to 60.10 ISO. Waste papers treated with enzymes also showed better brightness than those treated chemically. The brightness of the xylanase enzyme was higher (60.40 ISO) brightness than that of the 1% H₂O₂ sample from the waste books. In waste books, using detergent, 1, 2, 3% H₂O₂ and enzyme, the brightness was 56.01, 56.13, 56.36, 60.10 and 60.40 ISO respectively (**Table 6**). For writing paper, it was 70.56, 75.30, 76.02, 81.40 and 76.02 ISO correspondingly. (Green, 2012) found 92 ISO brightness in will copy paper and (Lee et al., 2007) found 92 ISO brightness in office work multi-purpose paper. Compared to waste books, writing paper provided better brightness as seen in **Figure 9&10**.

Figure-9: Brightness of Writing Paper (WP)

Figure -10: Brightness of Waste Books (WB)

Table 6: Brightness of writing papers and waste books

Treatment	Brightness of Writing Paper (WP) (ISO)		Brightness of Waste Books (WB) (ISO)	
	CSF(mL)		CSF (mL)	
	250	450	250	450
Detergent	66.2	70.88	50.21	55.41
1% H ₂ O ₂	76.78	75.93	51.68	52.34
2% H ₂ O ₂	70.07	74.41	51.4	55.33
3% H ₂ O ₂	79.42	81.4	57.14	59.18
Enzyme (0.02g)	78.5	90.64	62.64	74.8
Control	62.47	82.88	49.21	66.89

Conclusion

The study investigated the differences of treated waste books and writing papers physical, optical and mechanical properties. Reagents such as Detergent, NaOH, H₂O₂ and Enzyme (Xylanase) were added to this floatation pulping process. Preliminary experiments revealed that treated waste books and writing paper may produce brightness levels higher than 55 ISO but writing paper gave more brightness than waste books. Using 3% H₂O₂ in the case of writing paper treatment, brightness was maximum which was 81.40 ISO and for waste books, the maximum brightness level was obtained 60.30 ISO by enzymatic treatment. The physical properties of waste books and writing paper showed that tensile strength was slightly higher and tear strength was lower in waste books than in writing paper. So, we can conclude that in the floatation deinking process, writing paper showed a higher optical properties but slightly lower physical properties than waste books. So, for better brightness, floatation deinking is an appropriate process for writing paper. From a useful and economic standpoint, this procedure could be more affordable because of the minimal reagent use and running at room temperature. Larger-scale testing in the future is advised to assess this potential process.

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